

A methodological approach towards probabilistic impact chain analysis

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1 Introduction

The conceptualization and quantification of uncertainty is central in the debate on climate change impacts. On the one hand, it is important to be clear about the uncertainties associated with climate change and their associated impacts. At the same time, how those uncertainties are presented may cast doubt on the climate projections and legitimate skepticism among people without basic scientific knowledge. In turn, that situation can be easily misused by deniers seeking to amplify uncertainty in order to generate inaction and delay in climate change policymaking, as well as to discredit climate change research (Oreskes and Conway 2010). Notions of uncertainty can also add to other cognitive, affective and behavioural barriers to people’s engagement with the issue of climate change (Lorenzoni et al. 2007). Because **decisions** about climate change mitigation and adaptation will always have to be made under **uncertainty**, it is thus **critical** that we find ways to **guide such processes** (Willows and Connell 2003).

There is a growing need to quantify risks associated to the threats of climate change. To do so, it is not enough to identify climate hazards (droughts, floods, heat waves, etc ..), but also the grade of affection to the socio-economic system of the region under evaluation. That is, to quantify the possible consequences depending on the exposure and vulnerability components, (Fritzsche et al., 2014; Leis and Kienberger, 2020; Mastrandrea et al., 2010; Toimil et al., 2017).

Uncertainties in the estimates of the different components of the IC lead to unavoidable uncertainties in the risk assessment. Those include different components that are based on subjective expert opinion. In addition, future changes driven by non-climatic factors in the natural and social environmental (e.g population growth) are volatile, further increasing the uncertainty in the final estimate of risk (Fritzsche et al., 2014).

The main goal of this report is to propose a robust probabilistic framework that allow to produce a measure of the uncertainty associated to the risk assessment. An additional outcome is that through this process, it will be possible to assess the relative importance of each element contributing to the final risk and to identify the main sources of uncertainty. This document first describes the methodology and the different sources of uncertainty that have been identified within the Impact Chain framework used in the UNCHAIN project. Then it provides guidance on how to address these issues in practice using a simple case study as an example.

2 Probabilistic Framework

Our proposal can be applied to any functional form used to define the risk and whatever components are chosen. Nevertheless, for clarity here we will assume the Impact Chain framework where the risk is the result of a Hazard (H), Exposure (E) and Vulnerability (V). The basic idea is to consider that any component of the Impact Chain (indicators and weights) is defined not as a single value but as probability density function (pdf). The pdf allows to describe the uncertainty in a natural way, taking into account not only the most likely value (the maximum of the pdf) but also all the other values a given indicator or weight may have. The pdfs can in turn adopt different functional forms, being even empirical, although a conservative approach would be to use normal distributions (e.g. Gaussian) where just two parameters are required, the mean and the standard deviation.

For clarity purposes we first recall some key concepts of the Impact Chain approach. The risk assessment can be defined as (Equation 1):

$$R = W_{H \rightarrow R} \sum w_k H_k + W_{E \rightarrow R} \sum w_j E_j + W_{V \rightarrow R} \sum w_l V_l \quad (1)$$

Where H, E and V are the components that describe the Hazard, Exposure and Vulnerability respectively, and the W's refer to the Weight/Normalization factor applied to transfer those three components to Risk value. Therefore, the Risk can be expressed as a linear combination of H, E and V as follows (Ec 2):

$$R = \sum \alpha I, \text{ with } I \in H_k, E_j, V_l \quad (2)$$

In this regard, the main goal is to substitute each α and I by $f^\circ(\alpha)$ and $g^\circ(I)$ and to obtain $h^\circ(R)$ where f° , g° and h° represent a pdf. A simpler approach would be to use $\alpha \pm \varepsilon_\alpha$ and $I \pm \varepsilon_I$, so we can obtain $R \pm \varepsilon_R$, where ε represents the associated uncertainty to each element.

So, three sources of uncertainty may be considered. **Firstly**, the datasets used to define the different indicators are uncertain. For instance, climate models projecting the evolution of certain hazards are not perfect. Uncertainties associated to model numerics, model representativity or uncertain forcing will translate into uncertainties in the derived indicators. This is even clearer for indicators related to exposure or vulnerability where the available datasets are often limited or incomplete.

The **second** main source of uncertainties appears due to the nature of local decision-making processes on the topic of climate change adaptation itself. The relative weight of each indicator with respect to the final

risk can often not be objectified. This in turn, depends on the choice of the group of experts or on biases in their view of the particular issue. Thus, unavoidably, any kind of tuning based on expert judgement has associated a certain degree of uncertainty. In practice, this means that the definition of weights in the impact chain should not be addressed as an absolute truth but to allow some degree of variability.

Finally, the **third** source of uncertainty is the lack of key components on the actual Impact Chain. Limited knowledge of the problem at stake, or the lack of data may lead to the definition of an incomplete IC. That is, some indicators that could have an important role on the final risk may be missing. Therefore, some strategies should be defined to, at least, to try to bound this problem.

To sum up, these three sources of error must be taken into account to cover all the inherent uncertainties in any case study.

In this context our proposal is to define each element of the IC as a pdf describing the different values it can take. In practice, this means to keep all the possible values provided by the different datasets for a given indicator, or keeping all the opinions of the experts participating, for instance. If the full pdf cannot be described keeping the most likely value \pm and estimate the uncertainty will do (i.e., this would be equivalent to assume a Gaussian pdf). Then, all the components could be combined with the functional form chosen for the IC (e.g., linear combination, conditional combinations, etc...) to propagate the uncertainties till the final risk estimate. To do so, our proposal is to use a classical **Monte-Carlo technique** to propagate the uncertainties associated to each component of the impact chain. The IEO group can assist the different groups to implement it or to provide the scripts (to be determined). A graphical example is presented in the next figure. Each indicator is transformed from a single value to a range of values, represented by a probability density function. Then, a large number of combinations following the IC definition are produced to create a probability density function for the risk estimate.

Figure 1 Monte Carlo technique-based analysis of risk

A final step to evaluate the completeness of the IC and the assigned weights, is to check if the risk values can span across the whole range (i.e., typically from 0 to 1 or from 1 to 10). In other words, check if certain

combinations of indicators can lead to minimum and maximum values for the risk. This checking is not infallible but can help to identify if the IC has substantial gaps (i.e., missing indicators, ill posed weights,).

Finally, we propose an additional quantity to be computed, the “calibrated risk”, in which the final risk should be calibrated against historical data or experts’ opinions. The goal is to normalize the risk so it can be compared to other related risks. The risk that results from the IC evaluation provides a “relative risk” and is very useful to compare between different locations or different times. However, it may be of little help to stakeholders which need an “absolute value” to take decisions. For instance, one could find out that the risk of losing tourist attractiveness due to global warming is very high in a certain location when compared to other locations. But compared to historical events or to other sources of risk (e.g., political instabilities) maybe the increase of temperature should only be considered as a minor problem. Thus, our opinion is that it is important to do that final calibration to produce meaningful results for the stakeholders.

3 An illustrative example

In this section we use a basic example to illustrate the above mentioned concepts. For that we consider a simplified impact chain of Risk of loss of attractiveness by heat stress in a hypothetical region. Note that the example works only with few elements of what should be the actual IC.

3.1 Definition of the Impact Chain – Risk of heat stress for tourists

Here we define the Impact Chain as a fundamental first step to address the final Risk uncertainties for the example proposed (Figure 2). The IC’s are valuable outcome in themselves since they create a comprehensive understanding of climate change risk. In developing impact chains, expert knowledge and a sound understanding of the socio-economical system are indispensable, (Fritzsche et al., 2014). In this case we use a simplified version of the full IC. For instance, regarding to the Hazard component, not only the temperatures could affect the level of heat stress but also relative humidity or the wind may be considered to estimate the TCI (Thermal Comfort Index; (Teodoreanu, 2016). Besides, apart from consider the TCI, the TNI (Tropical Night Index) could be a representative factor of the thermal comfort during the nights and, thereby, could act as an important indicator as well. Likewise, for the exposure component, other elements could be included like the origin of the tourists (tourists coming from cold countries may be more susceptible to high temperatures than tourist from warm countries) or the wealth of the tourists (e.g. it is not the same to spend the time in a 5-star hotel which provides alternative activities and air conditioning everywhere than to stay in a 2-star hostel without the same facilities). Regarding the vulnerability component, other sensitivity factors could also be important like the lack of effective alert system for high temperatures, or the existing adaptability factors like promotion of tourism for less sensitive ages, to promote legislation to install air conditioning in all the hotels, etc.

Figure 2 Example of Impact Chain of Risk loss of touristic attractiveness by increased heat stress.

3.2 Dataset uncertainties

The datasets used to define the different indicators are uncertain. For instance, future changes in climate, and the effect they will have, cannot be perfectly predicted. First, the risk assessment of climate change impacts is bound to uncertainties because the magnitude of climate change depends on future greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions, which are unknown. Also, on top of the effect of GHG emissions, the natural climate variability can modulate the evolution of all the parameters of the climate system (e.g., different phases of El Niño). Furthermore, the climate models are not perfect and may produce biased results. Therefore, ensemble of climate models is used to have an estimate of the uncertainties associated to climate projections. In this case, we focus on the evolution of the temperature, which plays a key role in the heat stress assessment (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Example of the temperature evolution in a certain region

The temperature change could be translated to a thermal comfort index (TCI) and set it to a limited range from 1 (minimum hazard, TCI values not affecting the human activities) to 5 (maximum hazard, TCI values

that prevents outdoor activities). Likewise, the uncertainties in the temperature can translate into uncertainties in the TCI. In this example, we could consider that the region could get a hazard indicator of 2 ± 0.1 , where 2 is the index value and 0.1 the uncertainty associated due to the range of TCI projections:

$$H \pm \varepsilon_{\text{hazard}} = 2 \pm 0.1 \quad (3)$$

Here, for simplicity we have focused in the hazard indicator and assume the uncertainty in the exposure and vulnerability indicators is negligible. However, it is important to notice that the exposure and vulnerability components could also carry on inherent uncertainties. Regarding to the exposure indicators, historical data could be used to know how many tourists belong to vulnerable ages (<15 or >65 years old), but how the registration of this data has been carried on? Is the chosen sample representative of the total number of tourists?. The same problem could happen with the “type of activity” indicator. Moreover, if projections for these indicators will be used, the uncertainties could be very large. In practice, one can consider (as it is often done), that the exposure and vulnerability indicators will remain the same in the future, so the changes in risk can be clearly attributed to changes in the hazard (i.e. climate change). However, the methodology could easily accommodate uncertainties in those indicators as well.

3.3 Weighting/normalization uncertainties

In this section, we focus on the uncertainties associated to the procedure to obtain the weight of each indicator. In a first stage we deal here with the relative weights among indicators of the same type. For that purpose, we use first the example of the exposure indicators (see Table 1). In this case, we consider the percentage of tourists corresponding to each class for each indicator. For the Indicator “Vulnerable ages”, the 60% of the tourist are among 15 and 65 years old, and the other 40% correspond to tourists with less than 15 years or more than 65, and thus more vulnerable. With respect to the Indicator “Type of activity”, 45% of the tourists spend their holidays doing trekking, 35% prefer sightseeing and the rest of the tourists spend their time doing aquatic activities. The values of the indicator are set to span the range, from 1 to 10. Note that this is not relevant, as the weighting is what will modulate the importance of each indicator, not the range of values itself. For simplicity, here we consider that the indicators themselves have a negligible uncertainty.

Indicators	% of tourists	Value of the indicator (1-10)	Aggregated value
Vulnerable ages			
>15 & <65	60	2	4.40
<15 or >65	40	8	
Type of activity			
Trekking	45	8	5.75
City Sightseeing	35	5	
Aquatic activities	20	2	

Table 1 Values in percentage of the indicators considered to estimate the exposure component

The following step is to assign a weight for each exposure indicator in order that they reflect the relative importance of each factor with respect to the actual exposure. The different weights assigned to indicators can be derived from existing literature, stakeholder information or expert opinion (Fritzsche et al., 2014, module 6). In this example, we consider hypothetically that 6 stakeholders have been surveyed

to obtain the relative weights among indicators. To do so, two procedures can be used. One of them is through surveys, where different combination of choices is presented and the participant has to assign a final exposure. For instance, questions like:

- 1- “What would be the exposure (1-10) for a young tourist doing aquatic activities?”
- 2- “What would be the exposure (1-10) for an old tourist doing city sightseeing?”
- 3- “What would be the exposure (1-10) for a young tourist doing trekking?”
- 4 ...

Each question corresponds to a combination of different values for the indicator “vulnerable age” and “Activity). For example, the first would be 2 (young tourist) and 2 (aquatic activities); and the second would be 8 (old tourist) and 5 (city sightseeing). Then, we have N combinations of parameters leading to N values of Exposure (the answers to the questions). Using linear regression, one could obtain what would be the optimal weight for each indicator that would reflect the opinion of the stakeholders. Also, the regression provides an estimate of the error in the fitting (i.e., the uncertainty of the weights). For a more detailed example of application see next section.

Another option is to use the Analytical Hierarchical Protocol (AHP, Saaty, 1990), widely used in the risk assessment (Hsu et al., 2017; Lamata and Pelaez, 2002; Laura Tascón-González et al., 2020). This method is based on the comparison by pairs between different choices, which is easier than to consider multiple variables. A detailed description of how AHP works is out of the scope of this report. Nevertheless, in order to better understand this procedure, see the excel example attached with this report, which use four indicators considered in the exposure component (tourist age, type of activity, origin of the tourist and purchasing power) completed by one expert. A detailed explanation of how to implement the AHP can be found in <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J4T70o8gilk>. We have applied AHP with 6 participants, obtaining the weights listed in Table 2. The results from each participant can be significantly different. Thus, keeping not only the mean value but also the spread (or if a large enough number of stakeholders participate, the pdf), gives us a measure of the uncertainty in the weights. In our example, the age is considered to be slightly more important (weight = 0.58) than the type of activity (weight = 0.42)

Nº of expert	Weight of Indicators	
	Vulnerable ages	Type of activity
stakeholder 1	0.75	0.25
stakeholder 2	0.55	0.45
stakeholder 3	0.50	0.50
stakeholder 4	0.70	0.30
stakeholder 5	0.35	0.65
stakeholder 6	0.60	0.40
Weight (MEAN)	0.58	0.42
error (STD)	0.14	0.14

Table 2 Weights assigned to the exposure indicators through the AHP for each participant.

The same procedure (either the questionnaire or APH) could be applied to the vulnerability indicators to obtain their relative weights. As the procedure is the same, we do not repeat the example here.

3.4 Addressing the uncertainty of the Risk estimate

As a final step, in order to transfer the contribution of Hazard, Exposure and Vulnerability to the Risk, is necessary to estimate the relative weight between them (Figure 4). This is a problem very similar to what was faced when assigning relative weights to the exposure indicators. Again, this could be done through AHP, although here we present the questionnaire approach for illustrative purposes.

Figure 4 Scheme of risk equation

In order to obtain useful information about the issue at stake, it is recommended to suggest questions that lead one to think that depending on the case study, the components may not have equal weights (1/3, 1/3, 1/3), and therefore the Hazard could be more important than the vulnerability or vice versa, i.e.

For this simple example we propose to ask to the stakeholders several questions that represent different risk level scenarios. The goal of this procedure is to obtain the value of the risk provided by the experts depending on the scenario considered, (Table 3).

Question	How much the heat would affect the tourist if...	Level of Risk
1	It is very hot , the tourist is 70 years old and the health system is efficient	--
2	It is very hot , the tourist is 70 years old and the health system is NOT efficient	--
3	It is very hot , the tourist is 30 years old and the health system is efficient	--
4	It is very hot , the tourist is 30 years old and the health system is NOT efficient	--

Table 3 Example of survey for stakeholders to obtain relative weights among Hazard, Exposure and Vulnerability

It is worth to say the Table 3 is just a basic example, and the survey to each stakeholder could be much more complex and exhaustive. However, we aim to focus on the idea that in this process there are two main aspects that must be addressed, regardless the complexity of the surveys:

- 1) The questions must encompass different scenarios where the different components (H, E and V) can take diverse values.
- 2) Is important to keep the individual choices of each expert, so a certain range of uncertainty can be associated to each component.

The questions have associated values for hazard, exposure and vulnerability (see Table3), and doing a linear regression we get the weights (Table 7). Thus, we get a set of weights from the answers provided by each participant in the questionnaire. Here, we assume that the mean value of the weights provided by the stakeholders represent the “the most probable value” and the spread in the values of the weights, the inherent uncertainty. Note that the number of questions of the Table 3 may be much longer and include more variety of answers.

Question	Hazard value	Exposure value	Vulnerability value
1	10	8	2
2	10	8	8
3	10	2	2
4	10	2	8

Table 4 Hazard, exposure and vulnerability values associated to each question of the questionnaire in Table 3.

Stakeholder	Weight of Indicators		
	Hazard	Exposure	Vulnerability
stakeholder 1	0.6	0.28	0.12
stakeholder 2	0.44	0.3	0.26
stakeholder 3	0.35	0.35	0.3
stakeholder 4	0.52	0.22	0.26
stakeholder 5	0.36	0.35	0.29
stakeholder 6	0.46	0.27	0.27
Weight (MEAN)	0.45	0.30	0.25
error (STD)	0.10	0.05	0.06

Table 5 Weights among components provided by the stakeholders based on surveys

In our example, considering the results of the table 6, the contribution of the components in the estimation of the final risk is not equal. In this case, the Hazard is more “important” than Exposure and this more important than the vulnerability in the final risk.

3.5 Lack of components in the IC

A final check is recommended once the weights are computed. Now should assign different combinations of values for the indicators to see if we can recover risk values ranging from 0 to 10 (or 0-1, depending on

the chosen scale). This is to evaluate the completeness of the IC (i.e., check if there are missing elements). Also, it would be recommended to check with the experts or to compute the risk for past events. If the worst case scenario does not lead to what the experts think that should be the maximum risk, or what was identified in the past as a high risk, means that something is missed. Conversely, the minimum should also be possible to obtain with an appropriate combination of values for the indicators. Note, that this test does not ensure that the ICs are complete, but it is an useful diagnostic to identify missing components or ill-posed weights

3.6 A calibrated Risk estimate

As mentioned in section 2, an additional step would be to compute a calibrated risk estimate. Here the goal would be to put the analysed risk in context with respect to other related risks. In our example, the risk is to loss touristic attractiveness due to increase of temperatures. But for the stakeholders to act, they need to know how this risk compares to other risks of losing touristic attractiveness. For instance, a certain location may show a very high risk, but in practice the thermal comfort could have a minor influence in the choice of the tourists, compared to political stability or pricing

4 Final remarks

The proposed approach can be applied to any type of description for the uncertainties. If available, empirical pdfs or non-linear pdfs can be used to describe them. If there is not enough data to estimate those pdfs a normal distribution which only requires the mean, and the standard deviation is a good approach to describe the uncertainty. Also, a constant pdf could be used if there is no preferential value.

The practical implementation of this approach is done using simple scripts that propagate the uncertainties across the IC using a Monte-Carlo approach. At IEO we have them ready and we can apply them to the data of any of the UNCHAIN groups. Alternatively, we could envisage to prepare something easy to use that can be transferred so each group apply by themselves.

Finally, it has to be noted that the weight estimates, which account for a large part of the workload in this approach, are, to a large extent, universal and case independent. For instance, the importance of age with respect to activity may be the same everywhere, disregarding the IC analysed. This means that the experts' opinions collected in different consultation processes can be combined to obtain more robust estimates of the weights, even if they were linked to different ICs.

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